

Information Technology Company's Financial Analysis in India

^{1,2}Shilpa K, ³Dr. Krishna Prasad K

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

²Asst. Professor, Dept. of Computer Science, Nrupatunga University, Bangalore, India.
Orcid-ID: 0000-0001-7921-3540; E-mail: shilpaktr@gmail.com

³Associate Professor & Post-Doctoral Research Fellow, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Abstract: The purpose of the article is to make an attempt at analyzing the financial accounts of a chosen information technology company in India, mostly using certain ratios. Booming performance has been a significant issue for management due to the fierce worldwide competition in the market. Knowing an IT company's triviality is essential for evaluating its financial success because of its strategic value to the national interest. Due to its significant contribution to the expansion of the economy, the efficiency of the information technology industry has also taken primordial importance in a developing nation like India. With their cutting-edge technology and elevated service standards, newcomers to the information technology sector have played a leading role in India's financial system. Therefore, IT organisations are constantly looking for ways to restructure their operations for improved performance. With the power of financial statement analysis, these potential developments can be explored. Through the use of statistical tools, graphs, and tables, this paper exemplifies an empirical analysis of the financial statements of a top information technology business in India from several angles. It also provides recommendations for improving the sector's competitiveness. According to the report, Wipro Ltd. has continued to excel in the information technology sector over the past six years, with top-notch financial results. The article is effective for managers, stakeholders, and the foundation in general and offers significant springs of dexterity.

IndexTerms - Information Technology industry, Ratio, Financial statement, Performance, Management, Efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

The financial performance of a company is likely to increase in complex, dynamic circumstances where sustainable social and environmental behaviour is practiced. The financial markets place a high priority on moral and socially conscious principles. Including sustainability in business plans can have strategic advantages that enhance brand recognition and long-term shareholder value. The capacity to improve a company's corporate reputation as well as the ability to increase a firm's competitive advantage all support scholarly interest in sustainable development (Ambika, et al., 2017).

Using historical data extracted from yearly reports, financial analysis is a tool used to determine a company's current and future condition. Functioning of Analysis of solvency, liquidity, and profitability in terms of financial ratios, such as the current ratio, return on equity, capital structure ratio, return on capital employed, gross profit ratio, and operational profit ratio, is a component of financial analysis. The IT sector has been crucial in giving India a global presence that benefits the lives of its citizens by directly or indirectly advancing a wide range of business services, employability, top-notch technology, and living standards. There are four main IT-related industries in India: IT services, IT enabled services/BPM (Business Process Management), software & engineering, R & D services, and hardware products (Arjun, et al., 2014).

CSR and sustainability are strongly intertwined. CSR promotes sustainable development in three areas of business: social, environmental, and economic. The concern of stakeholders for CSR is directly tied to this sustainable development. Making development sustainable is the key to ensuring that it satisfies present demands without endangering the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Based on this definition, researchers and practitioners have attempted to understand sustainable development without ever coming up with a clear definition of the term (Bijendra, et al., 2017).

Businesses must be accountable for how their actions affect society and, in particular, the environment. The need for companies to report on their social and environmental performance and to be more transparent is growing. Through sustainability reports, which highlight their performance while focusing on the triple bottom line's three pillars of society, the economy, and the environment, businesses acknowledge their impact (Jain, et al., 2015).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past few years, India's tech exports have skyrocketed. Natural resources, benevolent indifference and helpful support from an otherwise invasive government, as well as good timing, have all contributed to its popularity. The vast majority of Indian IT exports have been comparatively regular services, such as low-level programming and support. There is much doubt regarding the ability of the Indian software sector to maintain its success given the tremendous development in demand for engineers and the relatively inelastic availability of engineers. This article presents the research's conclusions regarding the Indian tech sector (Raju, et al., 2020).

The share test is one of the coin-based exam structures, according to (Mathivanan, et al., 2009), in which proportions are employed as a yardstick to assess the financial state and performance of an organisation. An experienced examiner can have a more thorough understanding of the cash-related state and operation of the business by investigating and interpreting various bookkeeping percentages than he might have just looking at budget summaries. This research contributed to an explanation of the productivity and liquidity studies of IT organisations.

The presentations of 20 Indian IT businesses were analyzed in the study by (Akshita, et al., 2015) using ten financial metrics. The organisation is made up of elements that operate similarly but aren't quite like distinct organisations. A bunch analysis of the company and an example of a party were also examined in the study. Out of a group of 20 organisations, the method's results showed that Wipro is the best entertainer and consistently powerful, and that TCS is the only one in its private class, despite the fact that Wipro and Infosys are essentially the same company. Here, the medical classification also helped to identify the organization's implementation and provided crucial data to both economic specialists and forward-thinking investors, enabling them to keep investing in the organisation and developing creative mission strategies.

In her 2016 study, (Oden, et al., 2014) explored the extent to which board execution by company management affects the coin-related execution of a subset of Indian IT firms. The investigation ascertains if there is or is not a substantial relationship between a large portion of the board advisory enterprise (BC) and affiliation of the board (COB) and the ROA and ROCE of the selected IT organisations. The article detailed the annual evaluations of the top five Indian registered firms focused entirely on their well-known assets as of February 2016 in the interest of the Information Innovation Companies (especially TCS, Infosys, Wipro, HCL Technologies, and Tech Mahindra).

(Ambika, et al., 2017), the study featured the financial analysis in more major expertise relates to how much economic considerations are being or have been exercised and is a significant factor in the risk that executives face when dealing with money. It is a way to figure out how much a private corporate employer must pay as a result of its policies and duties. It is used to assess a company's well-known financial health over a specified period of time and may also be used to concentrate on similar groups in a specific industry or to examine well-known companies or industries.

Any form of commercial company needs different types of capital, especially fixed capital and operating capital, as (Arjun's, et al., 2014) analysis indicates. While short-term requirements call for running capital, long-term requests require fixed resources. The two capitals establish a partnership's effectiveness criteria in a corporate organisation. More competitiveness and gainfulness are made possible by better walking capital management, which is necessary to pay returns on the issuer's assets, which are frequently paid to investors. The choice of a liquidity position is made in the same manner. The proper supervision of reliable channels combined with contemporary assassination methods can result in successful working capital management.

Using ratio analysis, descriptive statistics, and other methods over an eleven-year period, (Pramod, et al., 2012) evaluated the working capital of five companies in the Indian IT sector. The report concluded with a summary of the company's financial statistics, utilizing ANOVA and hypotheses to examine aspects such as revenue, turnover, current and fast percentages, current asset on total asset, and current asset on current asset. In this investigation, these traits were also looked at. By using capital as effectively as possible, a corporation can achieve its ultimate goal of sustainability. Growth of shareholders' or members' capital is a worry (BC, Victory, 2009). Financial indicators like return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), net interest margin (NIM), capital asset ratio, total sales growth rate, and cost/income ratio have historically been used to assess the efficiency of banks.

Working capital management was carried out by (Swaran, et al., 2010) as part of a comparative examination of the cooperative industry. They used a variety of methods, including ratio analysis, t-tests, and operating cycle analysis. In addition to working capital management strategies, execution, and profitability actions, both sectors should concentrate on their liquidity and current asset utilization.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The sixteen financial measures (variables) under test are drawn from a variety of market categories, including per-share ratios, profitability ratios, liquidity ratios, and valuation ratios (Prusty, et al., 2016).

- **Per Share Ratios:** Earnings per share (EPS) is calculated by dividing the total number of outstanding common shares by the net profit of the organisation. A popular indicator for determining corporate value is earnings per share (EPS), which shows how much money a firm produces for each share of its stock.
- **Ratios of Profitability:** A class of accounting ratios known as profitability ratios is used to assess a company's financial standing at the end of an accounting period. Profitability ratios demonstrate a company's ability to generate profits from its business activities.
- **Liquidity Ratios:** A liquidity ratio is a calculation that shows whether a debtor will be able to pay off their short-term debt with cash on hand or if they will need to obtain extra capital to meet the amount.

- Valuation Ratio: A company's value is determined by valuation, which is a procedure in finance. When viewed in the context of a company's share price, valuation ratios act as helpful instruments for assessing investment possibilities.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The primary goal of the study is to use selective ratio analysis as a key method to examine the performance of Wipro Ltd., the chosen Indian IT company.

V. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The research is descriptive in nature and based on a wide range of financial statement-related literature. For improved knowledge development, descriptive research has been favored. Therefore, this study only uses secondary sources to gather data, including literature reviews, empirical studies, websites, books, journals, reports, etc. These secondary sources may all be obtained through academic databases and the Internet. The study is restricted to the years 2018–2019–2021–2022. The study has an inherent restriction in that the conclusions drawn from it may not be entirely valid since they are reliant on published data and information, which may not be entirely legitimate secondary sources. Additionally, just one company in the IT industry was considered, and only certain ratios were used. Therefore, if more IT sector businesses in India are utilized, more tools and methodologies can be applied, leading to more broad and effective conclusions (Kurbanova, et al., 2018). The scope of this paper is constrained to initially establish the significance of financial analysis. The impact of financial statements on Wipro Ltd.'s performance, the chosen firm in the information technology industry, has been identified as the primary mission that needs to be evaluated.

VI. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A significant portion of the Indian economy's GDP—more than 50%—is contributed by the service sector. The IT sector has been playing a prominent role in modern economy by advancing other fields with innovations, expanding service opportunities, influencing foreign exchange rates, improving lifestyles, etc. Investors frequently place their money with reputable, well-performing leaders in the IT industry. A company's overall coordination is bred by financial analysis (Sakai, et al., 2015).

VII. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

A company's financial records show its level of health. Before making any investment decisions, an investor reviews a company's financial statements. Statistical methods and procedures are used to try to determine Wipro Ltd.'s financial prowess and stupidity (Tabachuk, et al., 2018).

VIII. IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

This research will help investors and other stakeholders better understand the state of the Indian IT sector's finances and rate of expansion so they can further their own objectives (Izuymov, et al., 2017).

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher finds a research gap that is based on the fact that no previous study of a single IT company using specified ratios has been completed. But the following research holes remain for the future (Kilinc, et al., 2018): i) Analysis may become worrisome because the study overlooked inflation while examining trends across the study period. (ii) Objectivity established on historical data may not always be rewarded with success on the basis of which a corporation can make significant changes to its operations for hidden extraordinary demands. (iii) The qualitative spirit of a corporation is diminished by financial ratio analysis.

Table 1: WIPRO's Per Share Ratios

KEY FINANCIAL RATIOS OF WIPRO (in Rs. Cr.)	MAR 22	MAR 21	MAR 20	MAR 19	MAR 18
PER SHARE RATIOS					
Basic EPS (Rs.)	22.20	17.81	14.88	12.67	16.26
Diluted EPS (Rs.)	22.14	17.77	14.84	12.67	16.23
Cash EPS (Rs.)	24.85	20.83	17.19	14.17	19.31

Book Value [ExclRevalReserve]/Share (Rs.)	99.14	82.57	81.31	81.86	93.42
Book Value [InclRevalReserve]/Share (Rs.)	99.14	82.57	81.31	81.86	93.42
Dividend / Share(Rs.)	6.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Revenue from Operations/Share (Rs.)	108.67	91.80	88.22	79.75	98.83
PBDIT/Share (Rs.)	31.22	26.35	22.20	18.78	25.27
PBIT/Share (Rs.)	28.51	23.89	20.20	17.23	23.03
PBT/Share (Rs.)	27.84	23.15	19.27	16.36	22.18
Net Profit/Share (Rs.)	22.14	18.36	15.19	12.62	17.07

Fig. 1: Per Share Ratio

WIPRO Share Price Performance

- The share price of WIPRO has decreased from Rs 498.4 to Rs 469.1 during the past year, representing a loss of Rs 29.3 or around 5.9%.
- In the meantime, the S&P BSE IT Index is down 0.6%, trading at Rs 29,792.8. It increased by 3,661 points (up 14.0%) during the course of the previous year, from 26,131.6 to 29,792.8.
- The S&P BSE SENSEX is up 8.8% overall for the year.

Table 2: Wipro's Profitability Ratios

KEY FINANCIAL RATIOS OF WIPRO (in Rs. Cr.)	MAR 22	MAR 21	MAR 20	MAR 19	MAR 18
PROFITABILITY RATIOS					
PBDIT Margin (%)	28.73	28.70	25.16	23.54	25.57
PBIT Margin (%)	26.23	26.01	22.89	21.60	23.30

PBT Margin (%)	25.62	25.21	21.83	20.51	22.44
Net Profit Margin (%)	20.36	20.00	17.22	15.82	17.27
Return on Networth / Equity (%)	22.32	22.23	18.68	15.41	18.27
Return on Capital Employed (%)	27.32	27.49	23.62	20.44	23.87
Return on Assets (%)	15.09	15.30	13.29	11.36	13.16
Total Debt/Equity (X)	0.14	0.13	0.11	0.10	0.11
Asset Turnover Ratio (%)	0.82	0.77	77.18	71.82	76.20

Fig. 2: Profitability Ratios

Profitability Ratios:

- Return on Equity (ROE): The Company's ROE decreased and fell to 18.7% in FY22 from 19.9% in FY21. The ROE gauges a company's capacity to make a profit off of its investors' investment.
- Return on Capital Employed (ROCE): The Company's ROCE decreased and dropped to 22.1% in FY22 from 26.0% in FY21. The ROCE gauges a company's capacity to turn a profit using all of the money it has on hand (shareholder plus debt capital).
- Return on Assets (ROA): The Company's ROA decreased and dropped to 11.8% in FY22 from 13.8% in FY21. The ROA gauges how effectively a business uses its assets to produce profits.
- By December 31, 2022, Wipro have an operating profit margin of 12.94%.

Table 3: Wipro's Liquidity Ratios

LIQUIDITY RATIOS	MAR 22	MAR 21	MAR 20	MAR 19	MAR 18
Current Ratio (X)	2.23	2.50	2.78	2.96	2.86
Quick Ratio (X)	2.23	2.50	2.77	2.94	2.84
Inventory Turnover Ratio (X)	0.00	0.00	289.53	141.42	151.92

Dividend Payout Ratio (NP) (%)	27.10	5.44	7.93	7.16	7.05
Dividend Payout Ratio (CP) (%)	24.14	4.80	7.01	6.38	6.23
Earnings Retention Ratio (%)	72.90	94.56	92.07	92.84	92.95
Cash Earnings Retention Ratio (%)	75.86	95.20	92.99	93.62	93.77

Fig. 3: Liquidity Ratios

From 2010 to 2022, Wipro ratio was both current and historical. The ability of a corporation to meet short-term obligations is gauged by a liquidity ratio known as the current ratio. Wipro's current ratio was 2.24 for the three months that ended on December 31, 2022.

Table 4: Wipro's Valuation Ratios

KEY FINANCIAL RATIOS OF WIPRO (in Rs. Cr.)	MAR 22	MAR 21	MAR 20	MAR 19	MAR 18
VALUATION RATIOS					
Enterprise Value (Cr.)	327,315.40	222,962.28	106,910.41	148,400.15	129,726.08
EV/Net Operating Revenue (X)	5.49	4.43	2.12	3.08	2.90
EV/EBITDA (X)	19.12	15.44	8.43	13.10	11.35
MarketCap/Net Operating Revenue (X)	5.45	4.51	2.23	3.19	2.85
Retention Ratios (%)	72.89	94.55	92.06	92.83	92.94
Price/BV (X)	5.97	5.02	2.42	3.11	3.01

Price/Net Operating Revenue	5.45	4.51	2.23	3.19	2.85
Earnings Yield	0.04	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.06

Fig. 4: Valuation Ratio's

At the current price levels, the price to book value (P/BV) ratio is 3.9 times, compared to 3.2 times for the price to sales ratio. The price to cash flow (P/CF) ratio for the company was 20.6 times its operational cash flow earnings at year's end.

WIPRO Income Statement Analysis:

- On a year-over-year (YoY) basis, operating income increased during the year by 28.0%.
- Throughout the year, the company's operating profit climbed by 13.5% YoY. Operating profit margins decreased and were 20.9% in FY22 compared to 23.6% in FY21.
- Depreciation charges rose by 11.9% year over year, while borrowing costs rose by 4.7%.
- A 15.4% YoY decrease was seen in other revenue.
- The year's net profit increased by 12.6% YoY.
- During the year, net profit margins decreased from 17.5% in FY21 to 15.4% in FY22.

DU PONT ANALYSIS:

An important indicator of a company's total profitability and operational effectiveness is its earning power, often known as its ROI ratio. The relationship between profitability and activity ratios is demonstrated. By improving the profit margin per rupee of sales or by growing sales volume per rupee of investment, it is implied that a firm's performance can be enhanced. Shown in Table 5 are the Du-Pont model's parameters for Wipro. According to the data, its Net Profit Margin and Asset Turnover are reasonably steady and close to the average. Due to the low asset turnover ratio, even if it has benefited from debts, the high debt equity ratio has not been reflected in ROE.

Table 5: Du-Pont analysis of WIPRO

Year	Return on Stock (%)	Net profit Margin (NPM in %)	Asset turnover (AT in Times)	Return on assets (ROA in %)	Equity Multiplier (EM in Times)	Return on equity (ROE in %)
2018	39.21	28.73	0.81	23.21	1.56	36.20
2019	42.83	34.88	0.79	27.43	1.39	38.01
2020	-41.85	34.58	0.74	25.47	1.28	32.70
2021	-20.43	32.87	0.54	17.80	1.24	22.01
2022	6.93	33.90	0.63	21.23	1.25	26.46
Mean	-3.14	26.19	18.73	18.73	1.53	27.97
Std Dev.	57.66	7.09	5.10	5.10	0.22	5.87
Coeff Var	-1834.43	27.07	27.20	27.20	14.66	20.99

Suggestions:

- The beginning point of the profitability performance is often sales. The majority of forecasted profitability results are based on the anticipated level of sales. For a pertinent sales strategy to be developed and for the upcoming years' sales to increase, look to the IT companies.
- All costs, minus interest and tax charges, are included in operating profit. The IT companies analyse the fundamental earnings of the company and decide if debt or equity may be used in certain situations. On the basis of cost reduction and revenue growth, operating profit should be the main objective. As a result, businesses ought to intensify their efforts in order to boost operating profit for the following fiscal year.
- Analyze potential company performance while also gauging their profitability. It is important for IT companies to improve sales and decrease costs in order to generate net profit. Changing a product or service's price, as well as increasing its advertising or distribution, may boost sales and, consequently, net profit.
- The study period's companies had better long-term solvency than other IT companies, especially the Indian IT companies. As opposed to dividends on equity or preferred shares, the remaining enterprises should make the most of outside funding or debt with low interest rates.

X. CONCLUSION

India's IT sector is one of its most vital, active, and expanding industries. In specific ways, it helps the economy. Entrepreneurs are the epitome of those who are eager to invest in a business in the hopes of reaping significant rewards from its roaring success (Astrakhtantseva, et al., 2016). In the field of financial management, financial analysis is a receptive facet. Thus, the study has been started in an effort to examine Wipro Ltd.'s financial statements, the leading IT business in India, using financial analysis (Vasilev, et al., 2014). The essence of empirical research is analyzed with the aid of statistical tools and methodologies, which gives management reason. Results show that Wipro Ltd. maintains its leadership position in India across all metrics, and the company's resonant ratios ostensibly show consistent, robust financial growth in the years under consideration. Today's technology is changing on a daily basis, and IT organisations have a lot of opportunities to bring new knowledge in the relevant fields and address technological developments. The effectiveness of a company's operations determines how well it performs. The return on investment has evolved into a standard for evaluating the impact of returns on various operations. The margin will demonstrate how effectively the company has used its resources. Efficiency increased either through more efficient use of the capital that was available or by improving the link between sales and costs. (Vasilyev, et al., 2015).

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